

transparency do not necessarily increase and diminish respectively in a coagulation.

Work is in progress on the absorption spectra of a number of 'thermoaged' sols. These results will be published shortly.

S U M M A R Y.

The changes of viscosity and transparency (for white light) consequent on 'thermoageing' are studied for two oil emulsions and colloidal solutions of As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , MnO_2 , HgS , Fe_2O_3 and Prussian blue. The last two show change of colour. Majority of others show a decrease in viscosity and increase in transparency. In some cases, decrease in transparency is accompanied by a like change in viscosity, and *vice versa*. It is suggested that these properties, *viz.*, viscosity and opacity do not necessarily increase during coagulation.

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Received February 20, 1937.

SPIRO-COMPOUNDS. PART IV FORMATION OF SPIRO-COMPOUNDS FROM CYCLOPENTANONE. SYNTHESIS OF CYCLOPENTANE-SPIRO-CYCLOPENTANE AND ITS DERIVATIVES.

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It follows from the model that *cyclopentane* has got a coplaner structure, whereas the *cyclohexane* ring is in a dynamic condition changing from one multiplaner form to another, thus passing through an intermediate stage when it is coplaner and consequently a strained one. Now assuming that the average condition of the vibrating framework is between the uniplaner and strainless conditions, the difference in the case of formation and stability of the analogous spiro-compounds built up with these two types of rings will be a measure of the difference in strain in them. With the hope of gaining some quantitative idea of the nature of strain in these rings, spiro-

compounds with *cyclopentane* ring have been built up by a method similar to that described in a previous communication (Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 536). *cyclopentanone* cyanohydrin, obtained through its bisulphite compound, is allowed to react in alcoholic solution with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate. The sodio derivative of the condensation product, thus obtained, is treated with ethyl β -chloropropionate to yield diethyl 1-cyanocyclopentane-1- α -cyanoglutarate (I). This cyano-ester on hydrolysis by means of sulphuric acid (70%) yields a mixture of *cyclopentane-1-carboxylic-1- α -glutaric acid* (II) and its acid anhydride (III). The pure acid is obtained by treating the above mixture with caustic alkali (15%). The corresponding ester undergoes ring-closure in presence of sodium giving diethyl *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-3;5-dicarboxylate* (IV). In alcoholic solution this ester gives a violet colouration with ferric chloride and when hydrolysed by means of sulphuric acid (20%) gives *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylic acid* (V). The constitution of this keto-acid is proved by its oxidation to *cyclopentane-1;1-dicarboxylic acid*. This acid loses carbon dioxide when heated with the formation of *cyclopentane carboxylic acid*. The product (V) showed all the properties of a keto-acid. By the Clemmensen reduction of the keto-acid (V) a product (VI) is obtained which failed to crystallise even on keeping for a long time in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. It showed no properties of a ketone, but when the calcium salt of this acid is heated with lime in vacuum *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane* (VII) is obtained in a very poor yield. This hydrocarbon slowly decolourises a solution of permanganate. The product (VI) is heated with selenium for a long time with the expectation that a ring transformation will take place, but no definite product could be isolated.

The fact that the yield of the spiro-compound (IV) is of the same order as that of the *cyclohexane* analogue (*cf.* Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*) shows that the difference in strain in *cyclohexane* and a *cyclopentane* ring is not of a very high order.

In this connection it may be mentioned that there is a difference in stability among the spiro-hydrocarbons (a) *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclohexane*, (b) *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane* and (c) *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane* as regards the action of permanganate on them. Compound (a) does not decolourise a solution of permanganate (*cf.* Norris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 245), whereas (b) and (c) decolourise a solution of permanganate slowly. This suggests that in a spiro-hydrocarbon the presence of *cyclopentane* ring makes it slightly unstable.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Diethyl 1-cyanocyclopentane-1-α-cyanoglutarate (I).—To a well cooled solution of freshly distilled *cyclopentanone-cyanohydrin* (190 g.) in absolute alcohol (190 g.) a suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate, obtained from ethyl cyanoacetate (168 g.), sodium (33 g.) and alcohol (500 c.c.) was gradually added with vigorous shaking. The mixture after being kept in ice for 6 hours and at room temperature for 3 days, was mixed with ethyl *β*-chloropropionate (240 g.) and after initial reaction had abated, boiled under reflux

until a test portion diluted with water was neutral to litmus (about 40 hours). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate diluted with water and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with a large volume of water to remove most of the alcohol and dried. The ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b. p. 208° - $215^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$, yield 150 g. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 62.7; H, 7.1 per cent).

1-Carboxycyclopentane-1- α -glutaric Acid (II).—The ester (20 g.) was mixed with 6 vols. of 70% sulphuric acid and boiled under reflux for 12 hours. The condenser was removed from the flask from time to time to allow the alcohol formed to escape. The solution was then diluted with water and extracted with ether and the acid thus obtained was freed from neutral matter by extraction with sodium carbonate. The resulting product is a mixture of the required tribasic acid and its acid anhydride and it was heated on a water-bath with a solution of caustic alkali (15%) for 3-4 hours. It was then acidified and repeatedly extracted with ether. After removing ether the product was kept in a vacuum desiccator when it solidified. It crystallised from ether, m.p. 131° - 32 . This acid when heated with zinc chloride and resorcin gives a compound which shows bluish fluorescence on addition of alkalis. It is not much soluble in ether, yield 12 g. (Found: C, 54.3; H, 6.5. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 54.09; H, 6.5 per cent).

Triethyl cyclopentane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate was obtained by esterifying the above acid in an almost quantitative yield by alcohol vapour method. In a typical experiment the acid (25 g.), absolute alcohol (80 c.c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (8 c.c.), 3 litres of vapourised alcohol (3 hours) gave 28 g. of the ester, b.p. 162° - $65^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$ (Found: C, 62.3; H, 8.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 62.19; H, 8.5 per cent).

Diethyl cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one 3:5-dicarboxylate (IV).—A mixture of the foregoing ester (20 g.) and granulated sodium (2.3 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 minutes to start the reaction. The heating was discontinued until the vigour of the reaction abated and was then continued for 2 hours. After cooling the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried, and evaporated. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a pale yellow oil (9 g.), b.p. 180° - $85^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$ (Found: C, 63.8; H, 7.7. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 63.8; H, 7.8 per cent).

cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylic Acid (V)—The ester (IV) was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours and the cooled solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and

repeatedly extracted with ether and the extract washed with water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the ether it was kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid when it solidified in needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 67° after previous softening. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 7.6. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.6 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 232° . (Found: N, 17.5. $C_{11}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires N, 17.5 per cent).

Ethyl cyclopentane-spiro cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylate.—The ester prepared by refluxing a solution of the keto-acid (10 g.) in absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) with absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride, formed a colourless somewhat viscous oil (10 g.) b.p. $131^{\circ}-32^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 8.4. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.5; H, 8.5 per cent).

cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane (VII).—The pure keto-acid (10 g.), amalgamated zinc (35 g.), and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) were refluxed for 12 hours, further acid (35 c.c.) was added and the heating continued for 12 hours. After extraction with ether a product was obtained which even on keeping for a long time in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid did not solidify. This product showed no properties of a ketone but when the calcium salt was heated with lime *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane* was obtained in a very poor yield. The calcium salt and lime were well ground up together and heated in a distilling flask, the receiver being a test tube with a side-tube which was connected to the suction pump. The oil was fractionated several times, and a pure fraction of *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane* was collected at $60^{\circ}/12$ mm. It slowly decolourises a solution of permanganate. (Found: C, 87.3; H, 12.6. C_9H_{16} requires C, 87.09; H, 12.9 per cent).

Oxidation of cyclopentane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylic Acid.—The keto-acid (V) was warmed with an excess of concentrated nitric acid until most of the red fumes disappeared. The resulting solution was then boiled for a few minutes and finally evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water and again evaporated. The semi-solid mass, thus obtained, was crystallised repeatedly from benzene, ether and light petroleum (b.p. $40-60^{\circ}$), m.p. 187° (lit. m.p. 187°). On distillation this acid gives *cyclopentane carboxylic acid*.

My sincere thanks are due to Prof. P.C. Mitter for encouragement and advice during the course of this work.